

MICRO-THERMAL, X-RAY AND RAMAN ANALYSES OF POLYOLEFIN INTERFACES

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SUMMARY

Polyolefin laminate interface was analyzed using scanning thermal microscopy, synchrotron micro-beam X-ray diffraction and micro-Raman scattering with high space resolutions. For linear-low density polyethylene (LLDPE) / deuterated polyethylene laminate, the thickness of the interface was evaluated as several micrometer, which increased by annealing. The adhesive strength also increased by annealing, correspondingly.

Keywords: Interface, Polyolefin, Scanning Thermal Microscopy, Raman Scattering, Synchrotron Radiation

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are composed of physically and/or chemically different substances, so there should be an interfacial region (interface/interphase) between these dissimilar components [1]. The interfacial region plays an important role for adhesion, reinforcement, water / environmental resistances of the composites. Many tools and methods have been proposed for surface analyses such as an X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, a secondary ion mass spectroscopy, an attenuated total reflection of infrared, an atomic force microscopy and so on. They provide useful information on the surface characteristics and properties of the polymer composites. However, most of them can not be utilized for the interface analyses, especially non-destructive evaluation method has been very limited. In addition, high space resolution will be needed because the interfacial region is localized between two substances.

In this study, we propose three different kinds of non-destructive methods for interface analyses, *that is*, scanning thermal microscopy (SThM), synchrotron micro-beam X-ray diffraction (μ -X-ray) and micro-Raman scattering (μ -Raman) as schematically shown in Figure 1 with their apparent space resolutions. SThM is one of scanning probe microscopes, where the cantilever is made of micro-thermocouple. Thus, the thermal properties such as thermal conductivity, thermal expansion/contraction and thermal endotherm/exotherm can be detected by scanning the thermal probe. We tried to adopt these techniques for interface analyses of polyolefin laminates, such as polyethylene (PE) / *isotactic* polypropylene (*it*.PP), and PE/ deuterated PE combinations. The correlation between the thickness of the interface and the adhesive strength, and its change by annealing was investigated.

Fig. 1 Schematic illustrations of scanning thermal microscope (SThM), synchrotron μ -beam X-ray diffraction (μ -X-ray) and μ -Raman scattering (μ -Raman) to investigate the interfacial region of the laminate between Polymer A and Polymer B with their apparent space resolutions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sample Preparation

Linear low density PE (LLDPE, Melting point (T_m); 107 °C) and deuterated PE (D-PE, T_m ; 125 °C) films were laminated by hot-press at 125 °C, 6 MPa followed by quenching in ice-water. The laminated film was then annealed at 90 °C for 2 h.

LLDPE (T_m ; 120 °C) and *it.* PP (T_m ; 160 °C) films were laminated by hot-press at 150 °C, 6 MPa followed by quenching. The laminated film was then annealed at 100 °C for 2 h.

The cross-section of the laminate was cut into rectangular shaped block using microtome, then the interfacial region was investigated as follows:

Measurements

In this study, the SThM probe, X-ray microbeam and laser beam for Raman scattering were scanned across the interfacial region of the polyolefin laminate.

Scanning thermal microscope (SThM)

The scanning thermal microscope (TA Instruments 2990) is a kind of scanning probe microscopes, where the cantilever tip is made of thermocouple. By scanning the probe across the interfacial region at the probe temperature of 65°C, two-dimensional map of thermal conductivity was obtained within the space resolution of ca. 1.5 μ m [2]. In addition, by heating the probe at 20°C/min, thermomechanical analysis could be performed, where melting point of each local point on the sample was detected.

Synchrotron μ -beam X-ray diffraction (μ -X-ray)

Micro-beam X-ray diffraction of the interfacial region was conducted using synchrotron X-ray beam generated at SPring-8 BL24 XU in Japan [3]. SPring-8 (Super Photon ring 8 GeV) is the world largest third generation synchrotron radiation facility. The X-ray microbeam (0.9 μ m (vertical) \times 1.7 μ m (horizontal)) formed using a phase zone plate was irradiated on the cross-section of the laminated films. By changing the sample Z-position step by step, the X-ray diffraction pattern at each position was detected on an imaging plate (IP). The X-ray exposure time was 300 s for each pattern.

Micro-Raman scattering (μ -Raman)

Micro-Raman scattering is a popular tool for the non-destructive interface evaluation, however, the space resolution had been restricted to micrometer level. In contrast, the Raman apparatus (Nanofinder 30, Tokyo Instruments) with the space resolution of 300

nm was used throughout this study.

T-peel strength

Adhesion strength between two films of the laminated film (sample width of 10 mm) was measured by a tensile tester (Shimadzu, AutographAGS-1kND) at 25°C. The films were T-peeled off at 180 degrees at 200 mm/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

LLDPE / *it.* PP Laminate

Figure 2 shows the X-ray diffraction profiles of the laminated films by changing the sample Z-position across the LLDPE / *it.*PP interfacial region. In the position (a), only diffraction peaks belonging to orthorhombic PE appeared. By changing the Z-position from the PE side to the *it.*PP side, the diffraction intensity belonging to *it.*PP α -form gradually increased, and finally only diffraction peaks from *it.*PP α -form remained at the position of 4.69 μm apart from (a). Chaffin *et al.* reported an interfacial thickness of 10 nm for PE/PP laminates by transmission electron microscopy image [4]. This value was very thin compared with that obtained in this study. On the other hand, Ougizawa observed a very thick interface (of about 60 μm) between PP and ethylene-propylene rubber [5]. The X-ray microdiffraction method was performed under transmission geometry through the 50 μm sample thickness, so the value of the interfacial thickness may include the interfacial roughness or may be convoluted with the X-ray microbeam shape. However, we here defined the Z-distance with co-existence of the diffraction peaks both from PE and *it.*PP crystalline regions as the thickness of interfacial region. According to the above results, the laminated film possesses an interfacial region of around 5 μm thickness. Judging from the diffraction peaks, crystallite size is almost same independent on the Z-position in this study. As described before, interfacial structure of the PE/*it.*PP laminated film will be influenced by annealing.

Fig. 2 X-ray diffraction profiles of the laminated films by changing the sample Z-position across the LLDPE/*it.*PP interfacial region.

Table 1 Thickness of the interfacial region and the peel strength of as-quenched and annealed LLDPE / *it*.PP laminate

	Quenched	Annealed
Interfacial Thickness by μ -X-ray (μm)	20	5
T-peel Strength (N/m)	596	117

Table 1 shows the thickness of the interfacial region, evaluated by μ -X-ray, together with the T-peel strength of as-quenched and annealed PE/*it*.PP laminate. The interfacial region of the quenched sample was four times thicker than that of the annealed sample. The peel strength of the quenched sample was also about four times higher than that of the annealed sample. In both cases, the peeled position was always at the PE/*it*.PP interfacial region. The quenched sample possesses a thicker interfacial region with entangled molecular chains of PE and *it*.PP during processing. The entangled chains act as anchoring points between crystalline lamellae of both PE and *it*.PP. This is the reason that the quenched sample possesses high adhesion strength. However, PE and *it*.PP are thermodynamically incompatible and form a non-reactive system. Thus, when the quenched sample is annealed at 100°C, further crystallization will be accompanied with phase separation. These induced the decrease of the interfacial thickness, which is considered to be responsible for the decrease of the T-peel strength.

LLDPE /D-PE Laminate

Figure 3 shows the two dimensional image of the apparent thermal conductivity and the micro thermomechanical analysis curves of the as-quenched LLDPE / D-PE interfacial region using SThM. Thermal conductivity of LLDPE is different from that of D-PE, so we could observe the interface as the difference of the conductivity contrast

Fig. 3 Two dimensional apparent thermal conductivity image and micro thermomechanical analysis curves of the as-quenched LLDPE / D-PE interfacial region using SThM.

Fig.4 Apparent thermal conductivity profile across the interfacial region of the as-quenched LLDPE/D-PE laminate using SThM.

between them on the image. In order to distinguish the LLDPE part and D-PE part, micro-thermomechanical analyses were performed at the positions of red-star and blue-circle, respectively. With increasing the probe temperature, the Z-position of the probe increased in both cases within their initial stage of heating. This reveals the thermal expansion of the sample. The inclination of the curve was higher for the red-star position compared with that for the blue-circle. Both curves suddenly dropped at high temperature. These drops correspond to the melting of the sample, where the probe penetrates into the sample. The temperature (111°C) for the red-star was lower than that

Fig. 5 Raman spectra of (upper) LLDPE and (lower) D-PE in the range 800-1400 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 6 Two dimensional Raman images of as-quenched LLDPE / D-PE interfacial region from the integral intensity in the range of (a) $1047-1107\text{cm}^{-1}$, (b) $962-1002\text{cm}^{-1}$, and (c) the line profile of the integrated intensity across the interfacial region.

(122°C) for the blue-circle. Judging from the temperature of this sudden drop and the inclination of the curve, the red-star is on LLDPE, and the blue-circle is on D-PE, respectively.

Figure 4 shows the one dimensional apparent thermal conductivity profile across the interfacial region of the as-quenched LLDPE/D-PE laminate using SThM. There is a gap in the thermal conductivity at the interfacial region. When the transition region is regarded as the interface, its thickness could be estimated to be $3\mu\text{m}$.

Figure 5 shows the Raman spectra of (upper) LLDPE and (lower) D-PE in the range of $800-1400\text{cm}^{-1}$. Though both of them are polyethylenes, the spectra were different each other. This reveals that polyethylene could be distinguished by deuteration using Raman scattering. The scattering peak appears in the range of $1047-1107\text{cm}^{-1}$ is assigned as $\nu(\text{C-C})_T$ of LLDPE, and that of $962-1002\text{cm}^{-1}$ as $\delta(\text{CD}_2)$ of D-PE, respectively. By integrating the intensity of these scattering peaks, two dimensional distributions of LLDPE and D-PE are expected to be evaluated.

Figure 6 shows the two dimensional Raman images of as-quenched LLDPE / D-PE interfacial region from the integral intensity in the range of (a) $1047-1107\text{cm}^{-1}$, (b) $962-1002\text{cm}^{-1}$, respectively, and (c) the line profile of the intensity across the interfacial region. The intensity of $1047-1107\text{cm}^{-1}$ peak was higher for the LLDPE region in Fig.6 (a). In contrast, the intensity of $962-1002\text{cm}^{-1}$ peak was higher for the D-PE region in Fig.6 (b). The intensity profiles in Fig.6 (c) crossed each other with the tapered curves, from which the thickness of the interfacial region can be evaluated as $1.5\mu\text{m}$.

Table 2 shows the interfacial thickness by SThM, μ -Raman and T-peel strength of quenched and annealed LLDPE / D-PE laminate. The interface thickness, evaluated

Table 2 Thickness of the interface by SThM, Raman scattering and T-peel strength of quenched and annealed LLDPE / D-PE laminate.

	Quenched	Annealed
Interfacial Thickness by SThM (μm)	3	5
Interfacial Thickness by μ -Raman (μm)	1.5	3.0
T-peel Strength (N/m)	80	148

from the thermal conductivity image by SThM, increased with annealing. This increase corresponds to the thickness increase measured by μ -Raman. The increase of the interfacial thickness suggests the chain diffusion across the interface was stimulated for the LLDPE/D-PE laminate, which is considered to bring the increase of the T-peel strength by annealing.

The thickness of the interfacial region evaluated by SThM is twice compared with that by μ -Raman. Intrinsically, the difference of the principle for these methods contributes to the difference of the absolute thickness. Especially, the effect of thermal diffusion on the SThM can not be ignored, which will be the reason for the thicker interfacial region.

As mentioned before, the decrease of the interfacial thickness was observed for the LLDPE / *it*.PP laminate by annealing. In this case, crystallization accompanied with phase separation and disentanglement will induce the decrease of the interfacial thickness, which is considered to be responsible for the decrease of the T-peel strength. This is very in contrast with the case for LLDPE/D-PE, where both of the interfacial thickness and the adhesion strength increased by annealing. Compatibility of chain molecules are considered to play important roles at the interfacial region of LLDPE / D-PE laminate.

CONCLUSIONS

The interfacial region of the polyolefin laminate was analyzed using SThM, μ -X-ray and μ -Raman. For the laminate, the interfacial thickness can be evaluated as several μm , which are very thick compared with those already reported. Upon annealing, the thickness increased for the LLDPE/D-PE laminate, but it decreased for the LLDPE/*it*.PP laminate. The T-peel strength corresponds to the interfacial thickness. Micro-Thermal, X-ray and Raman analyses, such as SThM, μ -X-ray and μ -Raman are found to be effective tools to investigate the polyolefin interface quantitatively, and non-destructively.

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